

Fig. 4: Bilevel optimization with dd-CMA-ES. Within dd-CMA-ES, the covariance matrix Σ of the sampling distribution is decomposed as $\Sigma = \sigma^2 D C D$, where σ is the global step size, C is the correlation matrix, and D is a diagonal scaling matrix. When scaled by σ , the diagonal entries of D represent the coordinate-wise standard deviations of the sampling distribution.

A Convergence Issue of CMA-ES

Figure 4 shows the internal behavior of the CMA-ES reward-shaping process. The validation fitness $f(\nu)$ gradually rises in early generations before plateauing, indicating that CMA-ES finds a good region of reward parameters during training. However, the sampling distribution fails to converge, as indicated by large and non-decreasing coordinate-wise standard deviations, and anisotropy persisting in the covariance matrix. We identify a primary factor for this convergence failure: *insufficient timesteps for lower-level convergence*. Due to computational constraints, estimating the optimal policy parameters $\theta^*(\nu^{(i)})$ by running PPO for only a limited number of timesteps (K) typically yields sub-optimal policies. Evaluating these partially trained policies produces inaccurate fitness scores, which in turn generates a false ranking of the candidate reward parameters. Because CMA-ES relies purely on this rank order to update its search distribution, these false rankings act as severe evaluation noise. CMA-ES is highly sensitive

Table 2: Wilcoxon rank-sum test comparing GERS against PPO and DR using the 5 final trial return for each task.

Task	p vs PPO	p vs DR
InvertedPendulum	0.0079	0.5476
Hopper	0.0079	0.0159
HalfCheetah	0.1508	0.5476
Ant	0.0952	1.0000

to such ranking noise, which misguides the covariance matrix adaptation and impedes upper-level convergence. However, resolving this by drastically increasing K is undesirable, as it introduces the competing risk of overfitting the policy to the training environments and worsening generalization.

B Train vs Validation vs Test Behavior

We observe that the improvement on the test environments closely follows the trend of the CMA-ES validation fitness curve Figure 5. After CMA-ES begins to increase the validation score, the test performance also increases in a similar way. Importantly, there is no sign of divergence between validation and test performance. This consistency indicates that the policy are not overfitting to the validation set, but instead, capture the signals that transfer well to unseen environments by the shaped reward that helps guide the policy toward behaviors that remain effective across different unseen environments.

C Statistical Analysis

Tables 1 and 2 summarize the final test performances and statistical significance across five trials. While GERS achieves higher mean returns than BasePPO across all evaluated tasks, Wilcoxon rank-sum tests [36] indicate that these improvements are not statistically significant when adjusting for multiple comparisons. Specifically, applying a Bonferroni-correction [4], significance threshold is $\alpha = 0.05/8 = 0.00625$. The lowest p -values for GERS versus PPO observed on the InvertedPendulum and Hopper tasks ($p = 0.0079$) still exceed the required alpha level. Similarly, the apparent advantage of GERS over DR on the Hopper task ($p = 0.0159$) is not considered significant under this stricter threshold. Furthermore, while DR yields higher raw mean returns than GERS on HalfCheetah and Ant, comparisons between GERS and DR reveal no significant difference ($p = 0.5476$ and $p = 1.0000$, respectively). Ultimately, after correcting for multiple comparisons, the performance variations between the methods do not reach statistical significance, largely due to the limited number of trials constraining the statistical test results.

Fig. 5: GERS Train vs. Validation vs. Test Score.

D Continuous Space Normalization

The environment features a continuous observation space with potentially unbounded value ranges in each dimension. To ensure numerical stability and facilitate efficient learning, we apply a dimension-wise hybrid normalization strategy to the raw continuous state vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ to yield the normalized state vector $\hat{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

D.1 Unbounded Continuous State Space

For unbounded continuous state variables, we apply standard Z-score normalization. The parameters μ_i and σ_i^2 represent the empirical mean and variance of the i -th dimension, respectively. Unlike standard online normalization where these values are continually updated, our approach utilizes pre-computed running statistics obtained from a pretrained PPO model. To ensure consistent state representations, μ_i and σ_i^2 are frozen throughout subsequent execution and generations. To maintain numerical stability in cases where the pre-computed variance is near zero, a small constant $\epsilon = 10^{-8}$ is added to the denominator. The normalized value is computed as:

$$\hat{x}_i = \frac{x_i - \mu_i}{\sqrt{\sigma_i^2 + \epsilon}} \quad (4)$$

Table 3: Environment parameter variation ranges.

Environment	Altered Parameters	Range
InvertedPendulum	Torso mass, Gravity	[0.1, 3.0]
Hopper	Torso mass, Floor friction	[0.1, 3.0]
HalfCheetah	Torso mass, Floor friction	[0.1, 3.0]
Ant	Torso mass, Floor friction	[0.1, 3.0]

D.2 Bounded Continuous Action Space

For environments parameterized with continuous action spaces, we apply a systematic clipping and normalization procedure. This ensures that the actions generated by the policy or environment mechanics are strictly bounded and linearly scaled to the standardized interval $[-1, 1]$.

Let $a \in \mathbb{R}^{d_a}$ denote the raw action vector. Let H_j^a and L_j^a represent the strict upper and lower bounds of the j -th action dimension, respectively.

To prevent numerical instability (division by zero) in degenerate dimensions where the upper and lower bounds are identical, we define an adjusted range denominator D_j^a :

$$D_j^a = \begin{cases} 1.0, & \text{if } H_j^a - L_j^a = 0 \\ H_j^a - L_j^a, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The normalization procedure first explicitly clips the raw action to respect the environmental bounds, and then applies Min-Max scaling. The fully normalized action $\hat{a}_j \in [-1, 1]$ for the j -th dimension is computed as:

$$\hat{a}_j = 2.0 \left(\frac{\text{clip}(a_j, L_j^a, H_j^a) - L_j^a}{D_j^a} \right) - 1.0 \quad (6)$$

where $\text{clip}(z, \min, \max)$ bounds the continuous value z strictly within the specified limits.

E Reproducibility Details

To ensure the complete reproducibility of our experiments, we detail the specific network architectures and algorithmic hyperparameters utilized across all components of our framework, which are summarized in Tables 4 to 6

Table 4: Detailed Actor-Critic Network Architecture and Layer Specifications

Component	Layer	Input Dim	Output Dim	Activation
Shared Feature Extractor	Linear Layer 1	d_{obs}	64	ReLU
	Linear Layer 2	64	64	ReLU
	Linear Layer 3 (Feature Dim)	64	64	ReLU
Actor Head (π_θ)	Hidden Layer 1	64	64	ReLU
	Hidden Layer 2	64	64	ReLU
	Output (Action Distribution)	64	d_{act}	Linear
Critic Head (V_ϕ)	Hidden Layer 1	64	64	ReLU
	Hidden Layer 2	64	64	ReLU
	Output (State Value V)	64	1	Linear

Table 5: Hyperparameters used for CMA-ES reward optimization.

Hyperparameter	Value
Generation	100
m (CMA-ES initial mean)	0
σ (CMA-ES initial step size)	0.1
λ (CMA-ES population size)	60
Lower bound	-5.0
Upper bound	5.0

Table 6: PPO hyperparameters used for policy optimization.

Hyperparameter	Value
Timestep	81,920
Learning rate	1×10^{-4}
Number of steps (n_{steps})	2048
Batch size	256
Number of epochs (n_{epochs})	10
Discount factor (γ)	0.99
GAE parameter (λ)	0.95
Clipping range	0.20
Entropy coefficient	0.00
Value function coefficient	0.50
Maximum gradient norm	0.50